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GEOGRAPHICAL ANALYSIS OF MALARIA INCIDENCES IN BADE LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, YOBE STATE NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The study analyzed spatio-temporal cases of malaria incidences in Bade local government area, Yobe North Nigeria. The objectives of the study were to examine the spatial distribution and temporal trend of malaria incidences in the area. Data on malaria for two years (2017 and 2018) were obtained from the Department of Disease and Epidemiology, Bade Local Government Area. Three-Way Analysis of Variance {ANOVA} test was conducted to determine the difference between months, population groups and political wards in terms of malaria incidence in the study area. The findings revealed that there were 202,164 reported cases for the period under study. Sabon Gari ward recorded the highest proportion (28.2%) of the reported malaria cases. About 42% of the entire cases occurred among five years and above (5+) population age group. Results of the 3-way Analysis of Variance further revealed a statistical main effect between wards ($F = 93.977$, $P = 0.000$), strong main effect among population group ($F = 74.841$, $P = 0.000$), strong main effect for months ($F = 5.750$, $P = 0.000$). Further, interaction effects between the three independent variables (months, population groups, and political wards) were also significant. Multiple comparison test using LSD and Duncan Ranking were employed to further confirm the results. The study concluded that the area is endemic for malaria as transmission occurs all year round and also confirms the existence of spatio-temporal variability of malaria incidence. The study recommends that individuals, community coalition, policy makers, Non-Governmental Organization should focus more on sensitization, town hall meetings and other means of engagements to curtail this challenge in the area.*

Keywords: Spatial, Temporal, Trend, Malaria

INTRODUCTION

Malaria is a mosquito-borne public health problem that has stayed for centuries within our communities. Among vector-borne diseases and infections, there is no other disease that poses much threat to human existence as malaria (Desta and Ensar, 2017). The disease is therefore regarded as the most prevalent and deadly vector-borne disease in the world (Dahoui *et al.* 2023). Despite the

tremendous progress achieved globally in the control of malaria, the disease remains endemic in the WHO African countries (Dhiman, 2019).

As at 2019, the World Health Organization (WHO) caveat that malaria is endemic in 109 countries; most specifically in four continents and of the 500 million cases of malaria estimated to occur annually approximately one million resulted in death. The report further revealed that there was an estimated

228 million cases of malaria worldwide; and the estimated number of malaria deaths stood at 405, 000 in 2018.

Regionally, Africa carries a disproportionately high share of the global malaria burden; thus in 2018, the region was home to 93% of malaria cases and 94% of malaria deaths with total funding for control and elimination peg at an estimated US\$ 2.7 billion in 2018. Contributions from governments of endemic countries amounted to US\$ 900 million, representing 30% of total funding (WHO, 2019). Nigeria suffers the world's greatest malaria burden, with approximately 51 million cases and 207,000 deaths reported annually (approximately 30% of the total malaria burden in Africa), while 97 % of the total population (approximately 173 million) is at risk of infection in Nigeria (WHO, 2019).

In 2018, the North East Nigeria Humanitarian Response (NNHR) declared that Yobe State is endemic for malaria and with only 255 health facilities providing malarial services out of 485 leaving a gap of 230 facilities without the services across the Local Government Areas which make the situation increasingly worrisome. Unpredictable security situations hampered movement of health workers in some local government

areas in the state. Drugs, and other medical supply services; access to secondary healthcare and referrals in remote areas were significantly limited. Activities of major partners in malarial control such as Sun Map were also limited in the State. These are among the major challenges in the fight against malaria in the state.

This research therefore, investigated the geographical patterns of malaria incidence in Bade Local Government Area, Yobe State. The objectives of the study were to analyze the spatial distribution of malaria reported cases and examine the temporal trend of reported incidences.

METHODOLOGY

Description of the Study Area

Bade Local Government area is located in the northern part of Yobe State. The area is confined within longitudes 10°02' E and 11° 11' E of the Greenwich Meridian and latitudes 12° 48' N and 12° 88'N of the Equator with an elevation of 229m above sea level; and with a total land area of about 772 km² (Ahmed and Kafayos, 2020). Bade Local Government Area shares border with Karasuwa LGA to the north, Yusufari LGA to the North-East, and South-East and to the East with Bursari LGA; to the South with Jakusko LGA, and to the West with Jigawa State (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Bade Local Government Source: NASRDA, 2012

Bade Local Government is characterized by high temperature and seasonal rainfall. The mean minimum temperature ranges between 10-12 °C in December /January while the mean maximum temperature is about 37-42 °C from March-May in most part of the year. The period of rainy season lasts for about 120 days (June to September). The mean rainfall ranges

from 300 mm to 500 mm per annum (Alhassan *et al.*, 2018).

The predominant vegetation type in Bade is Sahel Savannah consisting of open thorny savannah with some short trees and grasses. The trees are about 5m to 10m high (Alhassan *et al.*, 2018). The relief of the area can be

described as generally low land with some undulation in some parts having an elevation of 229 m above sea level (Ibrahim, 2017 and Suleiman, 2007). According to the 2006 Population Census, Bade Local Government Area had a total population of 139, 804 (FGN, 2007). The 2016 projected population of Bade Local Government Area was 331 000 (NBS, 2017).

Materials and Methods

The data used for the study includes malarial records of patients diagnosed with malaria parasites. The data was obtained from Bade Local Government Disease & Epidemiology Department. The Departments was saddled with the responsibility to collate all cases of diseases clinically diagnosed at various public and private health facilities in the Local Government Area. Monthly malaria cases for two years (2017 and 2018) were collected from the Department. The selection of this period was based on data availability. Records of previous years were missing due to insurgency in the State. The data was aggregated in to three population groups viz: under five years (U5), five years and above (5+) and pregnant women (PW) respectively.

Statistical analyses were performed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences

Software (SPSS) version 21.0. Descriptive statistics such as frequency tables, charts and maps were used to summarized and display results. Three-way Analysis of Variance (3-way ANOVA) was conducted to determine the differences between months, population groups and political wards in terms of malaria incidence across Bade Local Government Area. Reported cases of malaria was considered as the dependent variable whereas population group (<5, >5, PW), political wards and months were considered as independent variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Spatial Distribution of Malaria Cases

The study discovered that there were 202, 164 cases recorded between 2017 and 2018 and the result is presented in Table 1. From the result, 28.2% of the cases were recorded in Sabon Gari ward. This was followed by L/Musa ward which recorded 20.4%. Katuzu ward has the least proportion (1%) of the reported cases. Table 1 further shows that malaria cases are higher among individuals who are five years and above. This group accounted for 41.92% of the total recorded cases. Pregnant women recorded the lowest proportion (22.72%) of cases for the period under study.

Table 1: Distribution of Malaria Reported Cases by Political Wards

wards	Total cases	percentage	U5	5+	PW
DAGONA	19916	9.9	7034	8192	4690
G/KURA	10809	5.3	4561	3856	2392
KATUZU	1979	1.0	224	1705	50
L/MUSA	41266	20.4	9891	15286	16089
L/FANNA	12677	6.3	6141	5359	1177
S/GARI	17263	28.2	20721	23417	12797
S/TAGALI	26835	13.3	11090	12621	3124
S/HAUSA	12498	6.2	5309	5295	1894
USUR/DW	15420	7.6	5475	6454	3491
ZANGO	3829	1.9	1030	2575	224
TOTAL	202 164	100.0	71476	84760	45928
Percentage			35.36	41.92	22.72

Source: Disease & Epidemiology Department, Bade LGA, (2019)

The analysis of this study showed that malaria cases occurred across all the political wards. However, higher number of cases was associated with highly populated wards. For example, Sabon Gari and Lawan Musa wards were the most built-up areas where population concentrates and are characterized with predominance of open drainage channels in which water is either moving slowly or not moving at all. Standing water around residential places serves as important habitat for a range of disease vectors including mosquitoes.

In addition, numerous unauthorized open dump sites are located very near to dwelling units in the area. Such dumping sites contained objects like discarded tins, tyres, leather and other containers that can store water and form alternative sites for the development of mosquitoes. These conditions provide suitable breeding sites for the vector mosquitoes thereby promoting the spread of

malaria incidence. In addition to this, most of the houses in the area are made with local building materials such as mud bricks and thatch. Houses made with mud are mainly characterized with large cracks and crevices. Cracks in the walls of building serves as resting place for mosquitoes and therefore, exposing residents to mosquito invasion (Ugwu, 2015). Thatched roof had been reported to provide a cool and shaded cover for mosquitoes during the day before moving out at night to feed (Amani *et al.* 2014).

Outdoor activities at night such as sleeping and relaxing during hot weather conditions is among others contributes to high malaria incidences in these wards. The finding of the present study supported previous works by Adekiya, (2008), Nasir *et al.* (2015), Sarwa (2015), Suleman *et al.* (2015), Mokoulu *et al.* (2016), Ibor *et al.* (2017) who confirmed that drains with stagnant water and garbage

dumpsites are excellent breeding sites and are therefore predictors of malaria incidence.

The analysis of this study further revealed a high occurrence of malaria among people within the age bracket of five years and above. This finding is aligned with the results of other studies by Yimar *et al.* (2015), Dawaki *et al.* (2016), Hussin *et al.* (2020), Solomon *et al.* (2020), Yakudima (2023) who also reported higher incidence of malaria among population of five years and above. The possible reason for the high occurrence of malaria among this population group could be linked with their mobility behavior. They are always on the move to schools, football fields, farms,

markets among other places and therefore exposed to mosquito bites. The low occurrence of malaria observed among pregnant women can be attributed to high priority given to them in term of preventive care such as free distribution of mosquito nets and anti-malarial drugs, to avoid morbidity and subsequent mortality.

Monthly Trend in Malaria Reported Cases

Table 2 reflects the monthly trend of reported cases of the occurrences of malaria incidence in the study area. The months of July, August, and September recorded more cases of malaria reports of about 28%. The period covering months of January, February and March has the lowest recorded cases with 21.3%.

Table 2: Quarterly Distribution of Malaria Cases

Periods	Number of Cases	percentage
Jan – Mar	43021	21.3
Apr – Jun	53181	26.3
Jul – Sep	56545	28.0
Oct – Dec	49417	24.4
Total	202,164	100

Source: Author’s computation, (2019)

Figure 2 gives a clearer picture of the seasonal trend in the distribution of malaria cases. The findings of this study showed that

malaria cases were recorded throughout the year with seasonal variation, indicating that the disease is endemic in the area. The study shows a pattern with marked effect of the rainy season and high malaria cases concentrated between the months of July to September which coincides with the rainy period in the area. During this period alternative breeding sites are more available resulting from rain water which collects in ponds, ditches and other low-lying surfaces thereby supporting mosquitoes. This finding corroborates Nanvyat *et al.* (2017), Epopa *et al.* (2019), Yakudima (2023) who also reported high incidence of malaria cases in the rainy season.

Figure 2: Monthly Trend of Malaria Distribution

Source: Author’s computation, 2019

Spatio-Temporal Distribution of Malaria Reported Case

The spatio-temporal malaria reported cases in Bade local government is shown in Figures 3 and 4. In the year 2017, the wards with the highest malaria reported cases are Lawan Musa and Lawan Audu (Sabon Gari) with cases ranged between 13,117 and 36,134. In contrast, the low reported cases were recorded in Katuzu ward (Figure 3). The pattern of malaria reported cases in 2018 is somewhat similar to that of 2017. Lawan Musa, Lawan Audu (Sabon Gari) and Tagalli/Sugum reported high number of

incidence. In 2018 the lowest reported incidence was also recorded in Katuzu ward (Figure 4).

Spatio-temporal analysis of malaria incidence indicated that Lawan Musa and Lawan Audu (Sabon Gari) wards have consistently recorded high malaria cases. The consistently high incidence of malaria cases in these wards may have been related to concentration of population which provides source of blood meals for mosquitoes, and indiscriminate disposal of refuse in waterways which resulted in the stagnation of water thereby providing potential mosquito breeding sites.

Figure 3: Distribution of malaria reported cases in Bade LGA in 2017

Figure 4: Distribution of malaria reported cases in Bade LGA in 2018

To determine whether malaria cases differ significantly among wards, months and population groups, three-way analysis of variance was conducted and the results were presented in table 3. The Table shows that all the main effects and the affected low order interaction effects were highly significant at **5%** level. The mean difference of ANOVA result shows that there is a very high statistically significant difference between wards and population groups as well as months and wards based on the post hoc test having $P=0.001$ which is less than 0.05 value. Similarly, statistical difference exists within population groups, wards and months indicating $P=0.005$ level respectively across the study area. This means that distribution of

malaria incidence varies between wards, population groups and between months.

These differences can further be explained using the post hoc test Least Significance Difference (LSD) and Duncan ranking to ascertain where they exactly differ. From the result in Table 4, the study observed that ward groups statistically differ between Dagona and Gwiokura, Katuzu, Lawan Musa, Lawan Fannami, Sabon Gari; Sugum/Tagali, Sarkin Hausawa, Usur/Dawayo and Zango wards respectively with values ($P=0.001, 0.001; 0.001, 0.001, 0.004, 0.001, 0.006; 0.001 \& 0.001$)but not with Usur/Dawayo wards.

Table 3: Three-way ANOVA Results

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	69022241.888 ^a	359	192262.512	4.523	.000
Intercept	54808638.612	1	54808638.62	1289.300	.000
WARDS	35954943.707	9	3994993.745	93.977	.000
POpgrup	6363028.525	2	3181514.262	74.841	.000
MONTHS	2688660.638	11	244423.694	5.750	.000
WARDS * POpgrup	13308453.864	18	739358.548	17.392	.000
WARDS * MONTHS	7220628.876	99	72935.645	1.716	.000

Dependent Variable: Malaria Incidence

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

Table 4: Malaria Incidence Ranked by political wards (Post Hoc)

	WARD_S	N	Subset						
			1	2	3	4	5	6	
Duncan ^{a,b}	KATUZU	72	27.86						
	ZANGO	72	53.25						
	S/HAUSAWA	72		145.81					
	GWIO-KURA	72		150.15					
	L/FANNAMI	72		176.06					
	USUR/DAWAYO	72		214.14	214.14				
	DAGONA	72			276.57				
	SUGUM/TAGAL	72				371.96			
	LAWAN MUSA	72					573.31		
	SABON GARI	72							769.94
	Sig.		.460	.069	.070	1.000	1.000	1.000	

Source: Data Analysis, (2019)

The post hoc analysis within population groups revealed that malaria incidence among under five years (U5) are likely to be similar to people who are five years and above category with mean rate of 370.61 while the least significant incidence are observed among pregnant women having the mean rate of 147.75 (Table 5). The least

significant incidence observed among pregnant women can be attributed to the growing concern given to this population due to its reduced immunity. Malaria control strategies mainly targeted the group as majority of morbidity and mortality related to malaria are attached to them (Yakudima, 2023).

Table 5: Malaria Incidence Ranked by population groups (Post Hoc)

	Populatio n group	N	Subset		
			1	2	3
Duncan ^{a,b}	PW	240	147.75		
	U5	240		309.36	
	5+	240			370.61
	Sig.		1.000	1.000	1.000

Source: Field Work (2019)

The multiple comparisons of months revealed that September, October, July and May are highly significant in malaria incidence with the mean rates (336.05, 328.72, 327.67 and 312.40) pair wise (Table 6). This means these are highest peak of

reported malaria cases seen across the study area based on the available data for the years studied. Increased mosquito population due to numerous breeding sites and favorable climatic condition is what responsible high malaria incidence in these months.

Table 6: Malaria Incidences Ranked by Months (Post Hoc)

	MONTHS	N	Subset			
			1	2	3	4
Duncan ^{a,b}	December	60	121.92			
	February	60	190.98	190.98		
	June	60		230.83	230.83	
	August	60			289.02	289.02
	November	60			289.18	289.18
	January	60			290.87	290.87
	March	60			294.55	294.55
	April	60			298.67	298.67
	July	60			312.40	312.40
	October	60				327.67
	May	60				328.72
	September	60				336.05

Source Data Analysis, 2019

On the other hand, malaria cases recorded in December and February were least significant to explain the incidence of malaria in the study area having the mean values of 121.92 and 190.98. The implication of this finding is that efforts to tackle prevalence of the disease in Bade Local Government Area should focus on the periods with highest mean rates; however other months with moderate malaria occurrence are not to be neglected. More so the LSD and Bonferroni tables further indicates that there is a difference between January and February as well as December ($p=0.008$ & 0.001), February and June show significance, December shows no difference but statistically significant with other months of the year ($P=0.008$, 0.006 , 0.004 ; 0.001 , 0.010 , 0.001 , 0.001 and 0.009). March showed difference with February and December ($P=0.006$ & 0.001); result further shows April and February, June and December are also statistically significant ($P=0.001$, 0.010 & 0.001), so also June incidences were statistically significant with May, July,

September, October and December ($P=0.010$, 0.031 , 0.005 ; 0.010 & 0.004).

CONCLUSION

This study provides valuable information regarding the local distribution patterns of malarial disease in Bade Local Government Area. The study revealed that malaria cases occur throughout the year but majority of the cases are concentrated in the rainy months. Of the three population groups (U5, 5+ and PW) studied, those belonging to five years old and above are more significantly affected by malaria. The results of the study further confirmed the existence of a marked variation in the malaria reported cases among political wards, months, and population groups. These differences highlight the need to focus on the most affected areas and target the rainy season during which malaria activities are at their peak for providing prevention and control measures in the area.

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